

Listening with My Eyes Wide Open: Researching Music Theater in Artistic Research Environments

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Abstract. In Pia Palme's "Mattetoline" (2019) the composer-performer brings on stage reverberations of a deserted island and its impact on her perception, which is acted out through different media and with two further musician-performers.

In my paper to the panel, I will reflect on my own attempts to approach this production as an example of contemporary experimental music theatre through the employment of listening, observations, writing and taking photographs as practices of my research as a theatre scholar. While I will focus on movement as a means of mediating between different modes of perception, I will also reflect on inevitable lacunae of the research process and impossibilities of capturing what is going on.

The shifting of perspectives and roles as a research practice is at the core of this paper. Shifting implies movement, on the physical as well as on the mental plane. Drawing on my own practices as a theater and performance scholar, I am interested in the question of whether and in what ways movement can connect and mediate the different perspectives of spectators and performers, of researchers from the realm of the arts and the humanities.

While pursuing a larger research project on modes of composing-performing in different art contexts, I witnessed different processes of artistic research. This led me to think about manifold approaches to research practices and concepts of knowledge. Regarding the general framework of knowledge production, I started to investigate the relations between the research practices I encountered and my own practices as a theater and performance scholar.

The association with two artistic research projects from 2019-2021 offered the occasion to conduct field research, engage in discussions and interviews, and experiment with different stages of immersion in selected phases of these projects.¹ While a broader reflection of these processes will be pursued at a different moment, in this paper I will concentrate on the research association with Pia Palme's project *On the fragility of sounds* at the University of Music and Performing Arts, Graz, Austria. Strands of discussions with Pia Palme and co-researcher Christina Fischer-Lessiak touched on the relation of music, performance, and theater, as well as feminist and queer research perspectives. The interference, overlapping, contrasting, or clashing of views due to different backgrounds were part of these discussions and are certainly a research practice in their own right. In this text, I will engage with

1. In 2019 I was part of Heike Langsdorf's artistic research symposium *Through practices*, 28.–30.10.2019, KASK School for the Arts in Gent, Belgium. See for reflections by the participants the contributions in Langsdorf/Arteaga (2021).

research experiences while witnessing Pia Palme's research and production of the music theater piece *Mattetoline*.²

Nodal points: artistic research and researching the performative arts

When first interacting with artists in the field of artistic research I was fascinated by the focus on research practices that spurred reflections on my discipline's own research practices. In fact, possible intersections of theater and dance studies on the one hand and artistic research on the other hand have been explored by authors like Gabriele Brandstetter and Gabriele Klein (2013), Isa Wortelkamp (2020), or Della Pollock (1998). All of them deal with the interrelations between dance, theater, and performance studies and the question of how one's position in an interdisciplinary space influences writing practices. The traditional dispositive of the relation between scholarship and art is organized along hierarchical oppositions. The writing and observing scholars are positioned on one side and claim an (idealized) objectivity, while artists are positioned as the opposite. While their geniality and originality are still relevant values, their insights are deemed to be flawed by subjectivism. The same division applies for the symbolic direction and the attribution of the gaze: scholars are imagined with a fixed position and gaze, as opposed to moving performers whose actions are objectified. In this set-up, the gaze is not returned.³ In accordance with Jacques Rancière's thought, I see this splitting and distributing of the aesthetic as a social dispositive (Rancière 2004, 2009). Rancière himself has connected it to the traditional theater situation, where activity and passivity are distributed among different groups (performers and spectators, for instance).

With my research design, I aim to find a different approach in order to circumvent these hierarchies. Two aspects are relevant in this context: First, experimental music theater as a genre is particularly apt to reflect on gazes because it entails a constant questioning of the relationship between seeing and listening and often destabilizes a fixed point of view. Second, the close relationship between theater/dance studies and some strains of artistic research indicates that the theoretical challenge of investigating the transient character of the performance leads to larger questions regarding knowledge production in general. However, these aspects must be considered as preconditional. Neither are all music theater productions conceived along non-hierarchical structures, nor does all research on the performative arts share the interest in non-hierarchical research set-ups. Furthermore, as applies for all research, the outcome and success depend on manifold aspects of the specific circumstances.

2. Pia Palme, *Mattetoline*, staged 12./13.12.2019, White box theater, Vienna, Austria. See: <https://www.fragilityofsounds.org/mattetoline-2019/> (accessed 29.11.2021). My role in this performance was limited to a researching observer. As such I was also present in two longer rehearsals in Vienna, where I observed the co-operation processes between the composer, performer, and sound designer. I also gave some advice on certain scenic questions. This didn't interfere with general concepts.

3. On the political-aesthetic distributions of the gaze see Phelan (1993).

On the general level another aspect is noteworthy: since most performances are performed with and in relation to an audience, questions of different angles and habits of perception encounter the very different desires of seeing/listening and being seen/heard which merge in the performative space. Performance theory agrees broadly on the point that a certain quality of the performance only appears and is then shaped in the mental and physical space co-created by performers and audience members (Fischer-Lichte 2008). This means that being in the shared performance space also entails further senses of perception – for instance, the kinesthetic or the visceral dimension.

According to my observations, processes of artistic research create a new angle in this relationship. The focus is mostly shifted from presenting an artwork as a defined aesthetic object (artefact or performance) to including reflections on creative processes and engaging with questions of how to present them.⁴ The question is, how does this affect the relationship between performers and audiences as well as between artists and scholars? One might add the provoking question: What happens to the scholar in this constellation? Is their mediating role rendered superfluous? Will the artist researcher become the new model of ideal research, as happened to the artist in neoliberal economic theories, where they were praised as the ideal creative and flexible, self-responsible employee?⁵ However, if one is not inclined towards dystopic visions, a different picture emerges. When taking into consideration different points of view, different backgrounds that shape different perceptual habits, and different research aims by individual researchers and disciplines, a rich field of new possibilities appears when a mutual exchange is enabled. The notion of the performance as a co-creative event or a relational artwork raises questions of how to connect scholarly and artistic research.⁶

In the artistic research environments I've entered, there prevailed an inclusive notion of researching *with* instead of presenting and researching *about*, echoing the idea of research *through* the arts instead of *about* them. Brian Massumi (2019), for instance, draws out this idea of *research with*, while Trinh Minh-ha suggests *speaking nearby* instead of *about* an artwork in order to avoid objectifications (Chen 1992). These expressions indicate the importance of relationships as well as spatial disseminations that resonate with strategies to de-hierarchize the gaze.

Regarding the context of experimental music theater and electronic music, consideration should be given not only to the gaze but also to epistemes of listening. While there are also

4. On the philosophical level an artefact as well as a performance can be considered an object of thought and perception. In the differentiation I refer to Phelan's description of the evolvement of performance art in consequent opposition to producing artefacts in the 1960s. The transient character of the performance was seen as possibility to refrain art and especially the image of women's bodies from the art market (Phelan 1993, p.e. p. 27).

5. See on this critique Reckwitz (2012).

6. Henk Borgdorff (2007) or Josef Früchtl (2019) offer models to place artistic research within existing models of knowledge categorization. Yet it remains to be discussed if these models really take modes of knowledge production in the differentiated field of the humanities into account.

hierarchies of listening that are connected to obeying, as Rancière (2004) shows, there are also possibilities for construing non-linear models of thought from the non-binary quality of resonances (Rodgers 2010; Minh-Ha 1996). While discussing the aesthetics and legacies of electronic music's female pioneers, Tara Rodgers highlights the importance of new models of thinking about historical and cultural processes:

Sound can be thought of as pressure and movements, doing cultural work. In the propagation of sound waves, the most audible impression may occur near the beginning of a sound's generation, but the wave reverberates through space indefinitely, continuing to intersect with and influence the trajectories of other sound waves as physical matter in ongoing interactions. Likewise, feminism and the reactions to them do not go away but continue to reverberate in shared discursive spaces. (Rodgers 2010, p. 18)

This observation on sound and the link with feminist activism is seminal, since it offers an understanding of the permanence of feminist concerns in society that is misrepresented by the stereotyped view on feminist history as grouped in stages or "waves." This observation also applies to other marginalized groups and their role in the arts. Non-binary thought models are a possibility to circumvent the linearities of a male-dominated canon. When 'sounding out' the resonances of female art (or art from other minority groups), different histories are found that are often overlooked. On the other hand, finding the right figure of thought is only the first step, as the term 'resonance' shows. While Rodgers unfolds its non-binary potential that captures historic connections and overlooked developments, it is most often limited to a harmonistic notion. On an epistemic level, Robin James (2019) demonstrates how sonic epistemes like resonances are connected to the rising importance of algorithms as means of regulating consumption (p.e. listening & watching) as well as other behaviors. In psychological contexts, the capacity of an individual to 'resonate' is often reduced to a metaphor for empathy. Both notions are based on the harmonistic aspect of resonance, while dissonant aspects, which form a large part of the spectrum of frequencies, are negated. In contrast to harmonistic notions, both Rodgers and Minh-Ha explore different aspects from a primarily feminist 'point of listening.' According to them, the physical and social meaning that is attributed to waves and similar echoing sound phenomena are perceived through listening *and* seeing. To highlight other bodily senses like the kinesthetic or visceral also changes the concept of both listening and seeing, since the influence of different states and positions of the body on these latter senses is thus acknowledged.

The figure as an epistemic concept

While reverberation and the related concepts of movement describe a rather fluid field of processes in the performative arts, a different notion is needed to describe more discrete objects that gain shape through these movements. In order to verbalize moments like this in the area of dance, Brandstetter and Peters (2002) have explored aspects of Roland Barthes' notion of the figure. This term not only refers to the discrete human figure, but also to

'figures of encounter' – and therefore a relational dimension underpins his concept. Barthes notes:

These fragments of discourse can be called figures. The word is to be understood, not in its rhetorical sense, but rather in its gymnastic or choreographic acceptance; in short, *σχῆμα* is not the 'schema', but, in a much livelier way, the body's gesture caught in action and not contemplated in repose: the body of athletes, orators, statues: what in the straining body can be immobilized. [...] Figures take shape insofar as we can recognize, in passing discourse, something that has been read, heard, felt. The figure is outlined (like a sign) and memorable (like an image or a tale) [...]. (Barthes 2001, p. 4.)

Following these considerations, Barthes describes the figure as a concentrated section, a cut-out from an ongoing movement, and Brandstetter and Peters develop this notion further to gain a method for analyzing dance. For my purposes, I also draw on Mikhail Bakhtin's view on the figure as a crossing point of temporal and spatial contexts (Bakhtin 2008). Like this, the figure can be conceptualized as an aesthetic shape in time and space. The figure as well as resonances are the coordinates of my research on relations of composing-performing.

On the grounds of this theoretical framework, I will now explore how these questions of scholarly and artistic research on the one hand and approaches to experimental music theater on the other hand, have shaped my research with Pia Palme's piece *Mattetoline*, whose stages of production and metamorphosis I observed from early in the development of the piece.

Research practices in relation to Pia Palme's *Mattetoline*, an artistic-research-informed music-theatrical study

Mattetoline is a piece which evolves through different media including music, film, an internet blog, and the stage. At a later point the piece was transformed into a radio piece.⁷ Here, I will focus mostly on the performance in Vienna in December 2019 and the rehearsals I attended as a researcher. With its wanderings through different media, *Mattetoline* bears traits of an open structure, a concept that was discussed in the Italian, French, and other postwar avantgardes and which inspired philosopher Umberto Eco to his notion of the 'open artwork' (Eco 1962/1989). While Eco and the music avantgarde of the 1950s and 1960s experimented with the relationship between the score and the performance, Palme takes her investigations further. Her concepts of composition and performance are inspired by authors from the current of New Materialism like Donna Haraway or Rosi Braidotti, who entertain the idea that the matter of which nature is composed is not inert but pervaded by vivid processes.⁸ Obviously, this assumption changes the relation of performing and

⁷ „Isolation Island – Reisebericht von einer Dämmerungslinie,“ broadcasted at Oe1, ORF, 02.08.2020.

⁸ The New Materialism takes up lost strands of older strains of materialist thought but different authors take them to different points. See on entanglements and differences Edwards (2010).

composing – which echoes the relation between the performer’s bodily actions and the composer’s thought – as these activities are no longer defined as strictly separated and opposed practices. This observation can be aligned to the research on experimental music theater that opens up a spectrum of possible conjunctions, fusions, and juxtapositions of the compositional and performative aspect (see e.g. Rebstock/Roesner 2012). In addition to that, some strands of New Materialism are concerned with processes of composition and decomposition in nature and culture, as well as creating processes that point to the performative quality of all materials.⁹ These aspects keep returning in Palme’s compositions; in *Mattetoline* she even takes quotes from Haraway’s book *Staying with the trouble* as a textual material for her composition.

Figure 1. Pia Palme live and as part of a projected video

⁹ This perspective has been elaborated by philosophers such as Jane Bennett (2010) and Donna Haraway (2016) or Rosi Braidotti (2019). An earlier articulation of this notion from performance theory is offered by McKenzie (2001).

Figure 2. Annette Schön Müller, soprano.

A laundry rack on a deserted island

The center of Palme's piece is defined by the artist's moving and listening on an island, the Finnish island of Örö in the Baltic Sea, where she stayed in 2018 as part of an artistic residency. It is a very specific location, since its unique natural environment is supplemented by ruins of the military history of the 20th century. The island was of strategic interest during the east-west confrontations and retains traces of having been close to such a strongly divisive border.

By following Palme's blog,¹⁰ where she uploaded short videos and observations from her sojourn, as well as from rehearsals and the performance itself, I as a reader-listener-spectator got drawn into the world of the island. The subsequently composed music theater piece can be seen as an attempt to transport this world as it is perceived by the composer's eyes and ears to the stage. For this purpose, Palme used recorded photographic, film, and auditive materials as a bases for her piece. In addition to live music making and actions of writing, text fragments are recited. An abstract scenic dispositive is created: Palme as composer-performer and singer Anette Schön Müller perform aspects of the performing composer-subject which engages an acoustic and visual dialogue with percussionist Manuel Alcaraz Clemente. Furthermore, acts of writing and speaking are brought onto stage. While Palme and Schön Müller present different facets of the creative processes, the musical actions of the percussionist are related in a dialogical manner. All three performers are visually present on stage and their interactions through movement and music making is

10. <https://piapalme.at/embedded-remote-security-blog/> (accessed 29.11.2021).

complemented by video projections and recorded and electronically processed sounds. Thus, different temporal layers are combined and brought into dialogue through the interaction of recorded and live generated sounds.

On several levels, the piece plays along with the genre of music theater. While there is no strong division of the succession of elements of the creative process, there remains a predominance of the compositional part. The relation between composing and performing is explored in experimental music since the 1960s (see Ballstaedt/Hinrichsen 2008). Palme also sets out to include the specificities and knowledges of performing into the compositional process and defines zones of liberty for the performers. The hierarchies between composing and performing are smoothed and sometimes suspended, but not completely abolished.

In regard to the different media, actions, and materials, the performance aims to enact and provide a certain wholeness of the aesthetic experience, which is created through multi-perspective perceptions and by exploring contrasts and ruptures as well as reverberations. A medium for this is one of the 'main' instruments of the piece, an outdoor laundry rack made from steel, that also inspired the title with the Finnish word "mattoteline." As a non-human 'actor' of the piece, it can be understood as a figure in the Bakhtinian and the Barthian sense, loaded with historic echoes as well as an object which is drawn into dialogue. The laundry rack is one of the remains of the island's military settlements, echoing a quotidian use that is no longer enacted. A documentary video, which is shown as a part of the performance, makes visible how sound material is generated in situ. Audiences can see the composer's knocking and rapping with wooden sticks on this laundry rack, thus sounding out and entering into a dialogue with its history as well as its future.¹¹ On stage, the percussionist Manuel Alcaraz Clemente responds to these sounds with metal gong instruments that echo the specific metal sounds of the laundry rack. The projected video material generates a further interactive layer: a dialogue between times and media, between the forgotten laundry rack and the percussionist's gongs, between the associations that linger in the energetic field created through the performing musicians and the audience's attentiveness.

11. More objects like this are drawn into dialogue and sounded out in the radio piece, like for instance a deserted bunker. They add to a performance that focuses on relations between human and non-human performers, as envisioned by authors of the New Materialism like Donna Haraway.

Figure 3. Manuel Acatrás Clemente, percussions.

Traversing medias and materialities

Pia Palme's compositional thought is mostly focused on listening, with an accentuation of its spatial and bodily aspect. The exploration of spatial, auditory, and visual aspects leads to a specific form of music theater that is strongly linked to aspects of electronic music. Performers on stage simultaneously act as musicians and anchoring points of the visual perception. From my view as a listener-spectator, they become figures that are vital for the dynamics of the whole piece. The piece refrains from outer dramatic interactions and enters instead the eerie atmosphere of the deserted island. Yet, the visual outer stasis is countered from within by the music and the tensions between the different voices. Phases of tension build up over increasingly longer, very concentrated periods and are then released, explosively at certain moments, thus creating a strong impact. This occurs for instance when the composer recites parts of the text and is drowned out by other layers of the music: a struggle of getting the words through is enacted. A similar moment happens when the percussionist's interaction with the laundry rack's sounds becomes ever louder and climaxes in rapid beats on a large hanging drum. The deep gong sounds reverberate and accumulate towards a density of sound waves. This action creates a strong visual impact as well as a strongly immersive moment. By creating a counterpoint within the different aesthetic layers, the dramatic aspect of the inward perspective is heightened by the seemingly outward stasis of the other performers.

The photographic eye

From my point of view as a researcher and while writing about performances, I constantly wonder about the best way to capture complicated processes like these resulting from

interactions, interferences, and reverberations between the musical voices, the media layers, and the live presence of the performers. Theater scholars are sometimes recognizable in the audience by their constant scribbling during a performance. Seeing, listening, and writing may become a combined action, an active way of reception and interaction with the performance at play. The writing not only captures transient thoughts and emotions, fragments of texts, but can evolve to becoming a haptic document, since dramatic tensions in the writing spectator can be released through the movement of the pencil, noting emotions of excitement and fascination as well as anger or boredom. In this way, writing is all but a rational, controlled act of taking notes; it is instead most certainly a very engaging matter.¹² In situations like this, the researcher is completely immersed while simultaneously taking note of this process. They themselves become a figure in the energetic field of the performance and through their perception the energies crystallize in textual signs. However, the immersive and transformative power of the performance is, as an utterly fragile constellation, not always taking place, nor is it always as intended by the performers. There may also be reflection through distancing, enabled by the complementary characteristics of theater and performance. These are equally important as moments of immersion: changing positions, entering and drawing back from a performative situation, experiencing with all the senses, closing the eyes or squinting from a distance at the performance. All are vital parts of the research process.¹³ The shifting of positions and accentuation of different senses at different times is a mode that is explored by some concepts of experimental music theater. To intertwine this aspect with practices and modes of research that highlight the autonomy of perception processes is a chance to broaden existing approaches. In this way, knowledges from different moments of the process can be included, and their harmonizing and dissonating resonances can be explored.

At the rehearsals of *Mattetoline* I tried a new approach to recording what's happening beside the usual scribbling: I started to take photos. Inspired by discussions on how to document the *Through Practices* Symposium in Gent,¹⁴ I considered setting up a score to investigate the rehearsals,¹⁵ but then I decided to use a camera to capture moments of attraction and tension that I experienced while listening. Like this, I hoped to combine the distancing aspect of the photograph and the route of immersion. I tried to capture the moments with the most intense sounds in relation to the ongoing visual action. This is certainly a challenging task even to professional photographers, since the translation between different senses and media is always accompanied by loss. However, as an experiment on documenting auditory and visual interferences in perception it was very

12. See on thoughts on the practice of writing Pollock (1998), Wortelkamp (2006).

13. Bertolt Brecht has established distance as an aesthetic and political aspect of his theatre theory; as much as Gertrude Stein. Hans-Thies Lehmann (2006) envisions both as relevant historic points of reference for postdramatic theatre concepts since the 1980s.

14. Heike Langsdorf, *Through practices*, 28.–30.10.2019, KASK School for the Arts in Gent, Belgium.

15. Working with scores has developed since the 1960s from musical or choreographic scores to enact quite complex processes of actions. By making use of scores, different social and political aspect can be investigated, such as the liberty of the performer or the audience, as well as the limitations of a set of regulations for experiencing a chosen situation.

valuable. The experience of taking photographs at the rehearsals spurred me to move through the room and to observe the performers and their actions more closely through the camera lens – from different positions of closeness and distance.

Furthermore, I thought of Roland Barthes' (1980) notion of a photograph's *punctum and studium* and took it as a starting point for my experiment. This concept, which relates to Jacques Lacan's (1986) concept of the "Real," enables Barthes to explore different planes in photographs: the aspect of 'studium' refers to a layer of information which situates the specific photograph in question in its specific context. In contrast, the moment of the 'punctum' describes a moment of punctuation that changes the information-oriented perception. It can be activated by a small detail in a photograph which suddenly strikes the observer, catches their attention and, from that specific moment, radically changes how they see the same photograph. Although this process occurs mostly unintentionally, Barthes has also developed a strategy for finding the punctum: he recommends closing one's eyes and noticing which detail of the photo is envisioned by the inner eye.

According to my observations, the notion of *studium and punctum* applies to all kinds of perception. Furthermore, it also sheds light on my heightened awareness when going to a performance. I am always curiously waiting for incidents that might change my perception, that give me a clue to make sense of what I am experiencing (inside and outside the theater) and/or offer a (temporary) transformation and reflection of everyday perception. Barthes' notion of punctum and studium even applies to processes of writing: from my writing processes I can tell that *punctum* often becomes the starting point for *studium*. It spurs the interest for writing on a performance and sets expanding research into motion. Within this process, the perceptual material is re-organized, re-structured – not unlike with psychoanalytic material – and reverberates in the written text.

When taking this thought further, experimental art forms, too, can be seen in a different light. Are they not circulating around the *studium and punctum*-relationship while confronting and deconstructing the particular art's traditional structures that are experienced as stiff and petrified? It seems to me that the dynamic of loosening traditional structures is at work, when experimental music theater experiments with the relationship between visual and auditory material, thus enabling the incorporation of new experiences and new expressions from the artist's side as well as more possible associations inside the listener-spectator's mind and sometimes surprising moments of sense-making.

In the case of musical theater, this process is supported by the different ways in which the visual and the auditory sources work on the level of physics. Sound and light waves have a different timing and temporality while traveling through space, as well as different modes of spatial dissemination. That is why these waves reverberate on the level of physics *and* on the level of constructing meaning, creating moments of significance, or phasing each other out, harmonizing or ebbing away slowly.

Stasis and dynamics of the fragmented self

Roland Barthes points out that the moment of punctuation is highly subjective, yet he himself gives a convincing example of how to make it traceable for other readers. This points to the possibilities of intersubjectivity as a mode of sharing knowledges that are situated within the individual bodies of performers and spectators alike.

Movement and photographs replay a relationship of stasis and dynamics, and if we follow Roland Barthes' theoretical foundations to Jacques Lacan's musings on the "mirror stage," a further aspect is unveiled.¹⁶ In psychoanalytic theory, the mirror stage marks the notion that within the forming of the self and its self-perception there remains an unbreachable rift – not so very different from the figure of punctuation. This is largely seen as a consequence of the fact that no-one can ever see him- or herself completely in a mirror, but only ever partially. Only fragments of the self are accessible, which are combined inside the mind. The missing parts are filled out by using the imagination. Yet this is a fragile process, which can be a gateway to the "false self" (Winnicott 1971) or forms of violence and self-harm. In addition, Brian Massumi indicates that we can never see our own body moving in the mirror.¹⁷ Another person might see the body moving from a distance but would not be able to connect this to the inner perception of the same body (Massumi 1996). A rift remains from all directions that makes a shifting research perspective between immersion and distance necessary. In addition, I would also argue that theater, dance, and music give different mediations and partial views of the relation of inner and outer perception. Combining the insights from different art forms and modes of research is like a mosaic – with fragments that keep changing and evolving independently through history.

While Lacan studies the symbolic significance of a missing reliable self-image, Massumi moves on to the structure of the visceral. This of course implies another level of reflection, which I cannot fully explore at this point, but would like to suggest, however, that it takes us again to the performative layer of materials and materialities. This layer can be explored by introspection, but also through the dimension of the haptic. Both have a strong presence in Pia Palme's piece, summoned there by the visual as well as the auditory, like the shuffling feet between paper leaves or pines, or leaves dropping and moving on the big drum. The spectator's mimetic or emphatic sensitivity might enable the somatic imagination of a shared introspection.

16. The concept of the mirror stage originated with Sigmund Freud and was later elaborated by Jacques Lacan (1986).

17. The only exception to this observation would be a moving shadow of our body. However, the shadow image is often distorted, and like the mirror image has been a source of the uncanny in literature, film and theatre.

Figure 4. Manuel Acatrás Clemente, percussions.

Figure 5. Annette Schön Müller, feet shuffling through paper leaves.

The different partial aspects of inner and outer selves are often reflected in performance art by the figure of the double, sometimes an uncanny doppelgänger. The augmented presence of video and digital images on stage in recent years in composer-performer's performances play with different self-images of the artistic subject (see also Lehmann 2019). This strain can also be observed in Palme's works. In *Mattetoline* she is present on different levels: as a

composer to whom the work is attributed; as a performer using her instrument and her speaking voice on stage; as a composer trying out in-situ material on the island of Örö; as a film maker providing additional video images. On stage, a fictional self emerges through fractions and multi-performer incorporation that are enacted by herself and the soprano, Annette Schön Müller. In Palme's following piece *Wechselwirkung* (2020), the position of the artistic subject is further multiplied and fragmented: it is present through different voices in the text and the music and is enacted on a certain level by dancer/choreographer Paola Bianchi, and soprano/dancer Juliet Fraser.¹⁸

Regarding these pieces and experimental music theater in general, questions about the consequences of the disruption of the visual-auditive continuum arise. Like the missing part in the body's outer perception, the visceral layer of the body is as invisible as sound is. Listening for echoes in the remnants of a vanished world (like on the island of Örö) and combining them with visual and haptic impressions might create a kind of access to this knowledge. Cognizance of the world and the self remains thus intertwined and reverberates between the inner and the outer perspective. A music theater that is organized according to non-hierarchical concepts offers a possibility of recognizing the limitations of each medium, and hence of the divided and hierarchized segregated fields of knowledge. Beyond this, there is a faint chance that the altered moments of perception might induce the wish of changing some of the "real" world's injustices, as Meredith Monk proposes (VanLoo 2009).

Acknowledging this, the gaze might be lifted from the rifts in perception, lifted from interpreting them as a symbolic trauma that haunts modernity and the mostly male artist.¹⁹ It might become possible to redirect the gaze away from the phantasmagoric search for the visual whole, relieved from the fear of the insecure, unstable relationship between meaning and matter and to direct it instead towards new questions: Might there not be discovered beauty in diffusion, in shattered images, in broken mirrors? And in bringing the broken pieces into dialogue, letting them reverberate, interfere and ebb away towards new meanings?

REFERENCES

- Bakhtin, Mikhail M. (2008). *Chronotopos*. Frankfurt a.M.: Suhrkamp.
- Ballstaedt, Andreas/Hinrichsen, Hans-Joachim (eds) (2008). *Werk-Welten. Perspektiven der Interpretationsgeschichte*. Schlingen-Liel: Editon Argus.

18. The creative process in *Wechselwirkung* is more complex, but a certain continuity of Palme's questions is discernable for me. I was part of this piece as a dramaturgic advisor, but the here presented view is strictly an interpretation of something emerging from the creative process that (regarding the here mentioned aspect) mainly took place between Palme, Bianchi and Fraser. I would describe my observation and argument as an interpretation, a practice of sense making, that was not verbally expressed in the piece or additional writings to the piece.

19. See on the construction of the artist subject in modernity: Foster (1996), p. 132; pp. 208–209. Phelan (1993, p. 5) argues very clearly on the connection of a phantasmagoric view of a (female) other and the emergence of violence.

- Barthes, Roland (1980). *La chambre claire: Note sur la photographie*. Paris: Seuil.
- Barthes, Roland (1977/2001). *A lover's discourse. Fragments*. Transl. Richard Howard. New York: Straus, Farar and Giroux.
- Bennett, Jane (2010). *Vibrant Matter: A Political Ecology of Things*. Durham, North Carolina: Duke University Press.
- Borgdorff, Henk (2007). "Der Modus der Wissensproduktion in der künstlerischen Forschung", in: Gehm, Sabine/Husemann, Pirkko/Wilcke, Katharina v. (eds.) (2007): *Wissen in Bewegung. Perspektiven der künstlerischen und wissenschaftlichen Forschung im Tanz*. Bielefeld: transcript, pp. 73-80.
- Braidotti, Rosi (2019). *Posthuman Knowledge*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Brandstetter, Gabriele/Klein Gabriele (eds, 2013). *Dance [and] Theory*. Bielefeld: transcript.
- Brandstetter, Gabriele/Peters, Sybille (eds, 2002). *de figura. Rhetorik – Bewegung – Gestalt*. München: Fink.
- Chen, Nancy (1992). "'Speaking nearby.' A conversation with Trinh Minh-Ha". In: *Visual Anthropology Review* 8.1, spring 1992, pp. 82-91.
- Eco, Umberto ([1962] 1989). *The open work*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Edwards, Jason (2010). "The Materialism of Historical Materialism." In: Coole, Diana/Frost, Samantha (eds, 2010). *New Materialisms. Ontology, Agency, and Politics*. Durham/London: Duke University Press, pp. 281-298.
- Fischer-Lichte, Erika [2004] (2008). *The transformative power of performance. A New Aesthetics*. London/New York: Routledge.
- Foster, Hal (1996). *The return of the Real. The avantgarde at the end of the century*. Cambridge: MIT Press.
- Früchtl, Josef (2019). "Artistic Research. Delusions, Confusions and Differentiations". In: *Eidos. A Journal for Philosophy of Culture*, vol 3, no 2 (8) 2019, p. 124-134.
- Haraway, Donna J. (2016). *Staying with the Trouble: Making Kin in the Chthulucene*. Durham: Duke University Press.
- Lacan, Jacques (1948). „Das Spiegelstadium als Bildner der Ichfunktion, wie sie uns in der psychoanalytischen Erfahrung erscheint.“ In: Lacan, Jacques (1986). *Schriften I*. Weinheim, Berlin: Quadriga, pp. 61–70
- Lehmann, Hans-Thies (2006). *Postdramatic Theatre*. London/New York: Routledge.
- Lehmann, Irene (2019). „Some Girls are Bigger than Others. Jennifer Walshe und Eva Reiter: Genderrelationen auf der Bühne der Neuen Musik. Zu Jennifer Walshe und Eva Reiter.“ In: Lehmann, Irene/Rost, Katharina/Simon, Rainer (eds): *Staging Gender, Reflexionen aus Theorie und Praxis der performativen Künste*. Bielefeld: transcript, pp. 130–151.

- Massumi, Brian (2019). *Architecture of the Unforeseen: Essays in the Occurrent Arts*. London: University of Minnesota Press.
- Massumi, Brian (1996). "The Bleed. Where Body Meets Image" in: John C. Welchman (ed.) (1996). *Rethinking Borders*, Houndsmills: Basingstoke, pp. 18-40.
- McKenzie, Jon (2001). *Perform or Else: From Discipline to Performance*. London/New York: Routledge.
- Minh-ha, Trinh T. (1996). "An acoustic journey." In: John C. Welchman (1996): *Rethinking Borders*, pp. 1-17.
- Phelan, Peggy (1993). *Unmarked. The Politics of Performance*. New York/London: Routledge.
- Pollock, Della (1998). „Performing Writing.“ In: Phelan, Peggy/Lane, Jill (1998). *The ends of performance*. New York: New York University Press, pp. 74–103.
- Rancière, Jacques (2009). *The emancipated spectator*. London: Verso.
- Rancière, Jacques (2004). *The Politics of Aesthetics. The distribution of the sensible*. London et.al.: Bloomsbury.
- Rebstock, Matthias/Roesner, David (2012)(eds). *Composed Theatre. Aesthetics, practices, processes*. London: Intellect.
- Reckwitz, Andreas (2012). *Die Erfindung der Kreativität. Zum Prozess gesellschaftlicher Ästhetisierung*. Berlin: Suhrkamp.
- Rodgers, Tara (2010). *Pink noises. Women on electronic music and sound*. Durham: Duke UP.
- VanLoo, Babeth M. (2009). *Inner Voice. Meredith Monk*, Film, 82 min, USA.
- Winnicott, D.W. (1971). *Playing and Reality*. London: Tavistock.

Images

All images were taken during rehearsals in December 2019 in Vienna, by the author, Irene Lehmann.

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Note: This contribution was presented at the 7th Study Group Meeting of the ICTM Study Group on Applied Ethnomusicology, which was titled "Performing, Engaging, Knowing." The paper submitted to the meeting was revised and peer reviewed for this publication. The peer review was conducted with open identities, i.e., the identity of the authors and the reviewers were known to each other.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7274048